

Comparison of Induction of Labour with Dinoprostone Gel versus Mechanical Dilatation in Unfavourable Cervix of Andhra Pradesh FemalesVasavi Korupolu¹, Roshini Gundapaneni²¹Associate Professor, Department of Obstetrics and Gynaecology, Nimra Medical College, Jupudi, Ibrahim Patnam, NTR district, Vijayawada-521456 (Andhra Pradesh)²Associate Professor, Department of Obstetrics and Gynaecology, Nimra Nagar, Jupudi, Ibrahim Patnam, NTR District, Vijayawada 521456 (Andhra Pradesh)

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Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract:**Background:** Induction of labor is a common obstetric intervention in developing countries. Pharmacological and mechanical methods are used commonly, such as prostaglandins and various intra-cervical catheters (single or double balloon) at the expense of many hindrances.**Methods:** Out of 280 pregnant women (gestation after 37 weeks) were studied. 140 pregnant women (group I) received dinoprostone gel intracervically, and 140 pregnant women (group II) were administered with catheter No. 18 through the canal with visualization of cervical OS. The balloon was filled with 50 ml of sterile water, and the catheter tapped on the inner thigh to maintain traction.**Results:** The baseline characters in gravidity, comparison of labor profile, maternal outcome, and maternal and neonatal complications had significant p-values ($p < 0.001$).**Conclusion:** It is observed that group I dinoprostone gel had more rapid cervical ripening, shortening induction to vaginal delivery Interval within 24 hours. Hence, the dinoprostone gel technique is more preferred than mechanical dilatation in an unfavorable cervix.**Keywords:** Bishop's score, Foley's catheter, tachysystole, cervical ripening, prostaglandin.This is an Open Access article that uses a funding model which does not charge readers or their institutions for access and distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0>) and the Budapest Open Access Initiative (<http://www.budapestopenaccessinitiative.org/read>), which permit unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided original work is properly credited.**Introduction**

Induction of labor is a common obstetric intervention, occurring in approximately 25% of term pregnancies in developing countries [1]. The increased caesarian delivery risk associated with inductions is strongly influenced by the induction attempt duration, especially with an unfavorable cervix [2].

Common indications for the induction of labor include post-dated pregnancy, preeclampsia and eclampsia, intrauterine fetal growth restriction, pre-labor Rupture of membranes, malformed fetuses, Rh-immunization, severe hydramnios, and abortion placenta, Intrauterine fetal demise, chorio-amnionitis, and maternal medical conditions like chronic nephritis, hypertension, and diabetes mellitus [3].

The contraindications to induction of labor include previous myomectomy, previous uterine rupture, fetal transverse lie, placenta previa, vasa previa, and invasive cervical cancer, and active genital herpes, mal-presentations [4].

Pharmacological and mechanical methods commonly used are prostaglandin preparations (PGE1 and PGE2) and various intra-cervical catheters

(single or double balloon); respectively, cervical ripening is a process of preparing the cervix for induction of labor measured by Bishop's score.

Hence an attempt is made to compare the stimulation of endogenous release of prostaglandin versus mechanical dilatation by insertion of Trans cervical Foley's catheter and pros and cons of both techniques are studied.

Material and Method

280 pregnant women admitted at Nimra Medical College, Jupudi, Ibrahim Patnam, NTR district, Vijayawada, Andhra Pradesh-521456, were studied.

Inclusion Criteria: Gestation age after 37 weeks irrespective of parity, singleton, cephalic presentation, intact membranes, and unfavorable cervix (Bishop Score <6). The patients gave their consent in writing for studies were selected for study.

Exclusion Criteria: Fetal malpresentation, rupture of membranes, multifetal gestation, abnormal fetal heart rates, fetal demise, previous cesarean delivery, or other uterine surgery (myomectomy, Cornu-

al wedge resection) and anomalous fetuses were excluded from the study.

Method: Out of 280 pregnant women, 140 are grouped as Group I (dinoprostone group), who received 2 mg of dinoprostone gel intracervically. Group II women were administered with a Foley’s catheter No. 18, which was inserted through the cervical canal with visualization of the cervical OS during examination with a speculum. Once past the internal OS, the balloon was filled with 50 ml of sterile water and the catheter tapped to an inner thigh to maintain traction. The position and traction of the balloon were checked once or twice on each hour, and the catheter remained in place until the balloon was expelled spontaneously.

All the women were monitored clinically for the progress of labor and fetal well-being. Protogram was maintained in all cases. When the Bishop score attained a value of equal to or more than 7, the membranes were ruptured artificially, or in cases of preterm rupture, oxytocin was administered if necessary. If Bishops score remains unfavorable, equal to or less than 5, after 18 hours of treatment in any group, there in those patients was further individualized.

The primary outcome measure was the induction-to-delivery interval; the secondary outcome was the incidence of instrumental delivery (including cesarean section). Uterine hyperstimulation with or without abnormalities in fetal heart, staining of amniotic fluid with meconium, requirement for augmentation with oxytocin and occurrence of postpartum bleeding. The neonatal outcome recorded was where the Apgar score was 5 minutes after birth, a necessary admission to the neonatal intensive care unit.

Duration of study was from November 2022 to November 2024.

Statistical Analysis: Base line characteristics, labor profile, material outcomes, maternal complications, Neonatal outcomes were compared with p-value. The statistical analysis was carried out using SPSS software.

Observation and Results

Table 1: Comparative study of baseline characteristics –

- Maternal age 25.52 (± 2.42) in Group I, 24.3 (± 4.20), and p < 0.921 (p-value is insignificant).
- Gravidity G1: 74 (52.8%) in group I, 60 (42.8%) in group II, p < 0.004

Table 1: Comparative study of Base line characteristics (Total No of patients: 140+140=280)

Base line	Group I (140)	Group II (140)	p value
Maternal age	23.52 (± 2.42)	24.3 (± 4.20)	p>0.921
Gravidity G1	74 (52.8%)	60 (42.8%)	P<0.004

- G2: 44 (31.4%) in group I, 48 (34.2%) in group II, and p < 0.005
- G3: 20 (14%) in group I, 18 (12.8%) in group II, and p < 0.005
- G4: 2 (1.42%) in group I, 14 (10%) in group II, and p < 0.001

Table 2: Comparative study of labor profile –

- Initial Bishop Score: 2.24 (± 0.74) in group I, 2.33 (± 0.80) in group II, and p > 0.351 (p-value is insignificant).
- Bishop score: >6 hour induction 8.32 (± 2.11) in group I, 7.64 (± 1.72) in group II, and p < 0.002
- Duration from initiation of induction to active phase of labor in hours: 4.56 (± 2.9) in group I, 7.43 (± 3.3) in group II, and p < 0.001
- Duration from cervix ripening to delivery: 5.76 (± 2.57) in group I, 6.84 (± 4.35) in group II, and p < 0.001

Table 3:

Comparative study of maternal outcomes –

- Mode of delivery:
- Cesarean section: 10 in group I, 29 in group II, and p < 0.001
- Assisted vaginal delivery 5 in group I, 7 in group II, and p < 0.004
- Vaginal delivery: 125 in group I, 104 in group II, and p < 0.001
- Indication for CS –
- Non-Reassuring FHS patients: 5 in group I, 6 in group II.
- Failed induction labor: 5 in group I, 22 in group II, and p < 0.001

Table 4:

Comparative study of maternal complications –

- Meconium-stained amniotic fluid: 7 in group I, 9 in group II, and p < 0.001.
- Fever during delivery: 3 in group I, 1 in group II, and p < 0.001.
- Hyperstimulation: 5 in group I, 2 in group II, and p < 0.001
- Nausea, vomiting: 11 in group I, 1 in group II
- UTI: 2 in group I, 5 in group II

Table 5: Comparison of Neonatal Outcomes

- Apgar score ≤ 4 at minute: 1 (0.71%) in group I, 2 (1.4%) in group II
- Apgar Score ≤7 at 5 minutes: 17 (12%) in group I, 21 (15%) in group II
- Admission to NICU: 14 (10%) in group I, 22 (15.7%) in group II.

G2	44 (31.4%)	48 (34.2%)	P<0.005
G3	20 (14%)	18 (12.8%)	P<0.005
G4	2 (1.42%)	14 (10%)	P<0.001

(p<0.005 p values are highly significant)

Figure 1: Comparative study of Base line characteristics

Table 2: Comparative study of labour profile

Labour profile	Group I (140)	Group II (140)	p value
Initial Bishop score	2.24 (±0.74)	2.33 (± 0.80)	p>0.35 (p value insignificant)
Bishop Score > 6hours after Induction	8.32 (± 2.11)	7.64 (± 1.72)	P<0.002 (HS)
Duration from initiation to active phase of labour (in hrs)	4.56(± 2.9)	7.43(± 3.3)	P<0.001 (HS)
Duration in from cervix ripening to delivery	5.76(± 2.57)	6.84 (± 4.35)	P<0.001 (HS)

(HS=p value is highly significant)

Figure 2: Comparative study of labour profile

Table 3: Comparative study of Maternal Outcome

(A) Mode of delivery	Group I (140)	Group II (140)	p value
Caesarean section	10	29	P<0.001
Assisted vaginal delivery	5	7	P<0.004 HS
Vaginal delivery	125	104	P<0.001 HS
(B) Mode of delivery	Group I (140)	Group II (140)	p value
Non-reassuring FHS patterns	5	6	P<0.004 (sign)
Failed Induction of labour	5	22	P<0.001 HS

(HS = p value is highly significant)

Figure 3: Comparative study of Maternal Outcome

Table 4: Comparative study of maternal complications

Maternal complications	Group I (140)	Group II (140)	p value
Meconium stained amniotic fluid	7	9	P<0.001 HS
Fever during delivery	3	1	P<0.001 HS
Hyper stimulation	5	2	P<0.001 HS
Nausea, Vomiting	11	1	P<0.001 HS
UTI	2	5	P<0.001 HS

(HS = p value is highly significant)

Figure 4: Comparative study of maternal complications

Table 5: Comparison of Neonatal outcomes

Neonatal outcomes	Group I (140)	Group II (140)
Apgar score ≤ 4 at minute	1 (0.71%)	2 (1.42%)
Apgar score ≤ 7 at 5 minutes	17 (12.1%)	21 (15%)
Admission to NICU	14 (10%)	22 (15.7%)

Figure 5: Comparison of Neonatal outcomes

Discussion

Present a comparative study of the induction of labor with dinoprostone gel versus mechanical dilatation in an unfavorable cervix. The groups of pregnant women were administered. Dinoprostone gel was introduced cervically, and in group II pregnant women, a Foley's catheter was introduced through the cervix to the extra-amniotic space using a sterile technique. In the baseline studies, the maternal age was 23.52 (± 2.42) in group I, 24.3 (± 4.20) in group II, and the p-value was insignificant.

The gravidity G1, G2, G3, and G4 were compared in both groups, and the p-value was highly significant ($p < 0.001$) (Table 1). Comparative study of labor profile Bishop Score >6 hours, duration from initiation of induction to active phase of labor (in hours), and duration from cervix ripening to delivery has a significant p-value ($p < 0.001$) (Table 2). In the comparative study of maternal outcomes in the cesarean section group, I had 10, and 29 in group II. In assisted vaginal delivery, 5 patients in group I and 7 in group II had significant p-values ($p < 0.001$). Vaginal delivery had 125 in group I and 104 in group II.

In the study of indication for cesarean section. In non-reassuring FHS pattern 5 in group I, 6 were in group II. Failed induction of labor: 5 in group I, 22 in group II, and p-value was highly significant ($p < 0.001$) (Table 3). In the comparative study of maternal complications, meconium-stained amniotic fluid was found in 7 in group I and 9 in group II. Fever during delivery: 3 in group I, 1 in group II. In hyperstimulation studies, 5 were in group I and 2 in group II. Nausea and vomiting patients were 11 in group I and 1 in group II. UTI was observed 2 in group I, 5 in group II, and the p-value was highly significant ($p < 0.001$) in every parameter (Table 4). In the comparison of neonatal outcomes.

Apgar score ≤ 4 at minute 1: 1 in group I, 2 in group II; Apgar ≤ 7 at 5 minutes: 19 in group I, 23 in group II. Admission in NICU 16 in group I, 19 in group II (Table 5) These findings are more or less in agreement with previous studies [5,6,7].

Pregnant women treated with dinoprostone as a slow-release vaginal insert were effective methods for successful induction of labor when compared with manual technique induction labor (8). It is also reported that the cesarean section rate decreased only in multiparous women who benefited more from the dinoprostone slow-released vaginal insert and multiparity was an indicator for successful vaginal delivery in women treated with dinoprostone gel in 24 hours. Although Foley's catheter is a cheap and easily available but underutilized method for cervical ripening with hardly any neonatal or maternal risks [9]. It is reported that Foley's catheter takes more time in the induction-to-delivery

interval compared to prostaglandin [10]. It is also reported that, in a study comparing PGE2 insert versus Foley's catheter for labor induction, no significant difference was noted in the mode of delivery or induction delivery interval between the two groups. However, PGE2 insert was associated with more cases of tachysystole and the requirement of a second method of cervical ripening [11]. Hence, the pathophysiology of the uterus and CVS profile of pregnant women must be taken into observation during the study of PGE2 insert patients because tachysystole may cause adverse complications to both the fetus and mother.

Hence, the dosage of dinoprostone gel and the body mass index of the mother must be correlated before administration.

Summary and Conclusion

In the present comparative study of induction of labor with dinoprostone gel versus mechanical dilatation in an unfavorable cervix (low Bishop's score). It is observed that Dinoprostone gel was more rapid in cervical ripening, shortening induction to vaginal delivery interval and increasing the number of vaginal deliveries within 24 hours. Such a study must be carried out in a large number of patients in a high-tech obstetrics and gynecology hospital to confirm the significant results of the present study because the factors and exact mechanism that cause contraction of the uterus during delivery are still unclear.

Limitation of study: Owing to tertiary location of research centre, small number of patients, lack of latest techniques we have limited finding and results.

This research work was approved by the ethical committee of Nimra Medical College, Jupudi, Ibrahim Patnam, NTR district, Vijayawada, Andhra Pradesh-521456.

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